

The revised version of the article, following peer review, has been published in the journal "Innovation: The European Journal of Social Science Research", <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13511610.2024.2442933>.

Advanced services as a new frontier of China's value chain cooperation with European manufacturing

Ewa Cieřlik

Associate Professor

Poznan University of Economics and Business

Poland

Email: ewa.cieslik@ue.poznan.pl, ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7230-8480>

Abstract

The article focuses on cross-sectoral analysis concerning services, especially ICT services, flowing from China to European manufacturing. A key research question is: considering the increasing share of domestic services in China's manufacturing in recent years, is there a similar trend in Chinese services exported abroad and incorporated into foreign manufacturing (servicification with Chinese value added of foreign manufacturing), particularly European manufacturing. Applying input-output models, the study showed the growing role of China as a supplier of ICT services to European manufacturing. It also identified the industries that are most dependent on Chinese ICT services.

Keywords: servicification of manufacturing, ICT services, global value chains, manufacturing industry, China, Europe

JEL: F10, F14

Declarations

Availability of data and material

Data is extracted from across OECD's databases TiVA. Processed data will be made available on reasonable request after the acceptance of the paper.

Competing interests

The author declares there is no conflict of interests.

Funding

The article is the result of the research project 'Digital Silk Road as a network of technological connections between China and Europe within value chains: towards win-win or decoupling?' financed by the National Science Centre, Poland (UMO-2021/43/B/HS4/01079).

1. Introduction

China's growing influence in the global economy has played a significant role in reshaping global value chains (GVCs) in the early 21st century (Su et al. 2021). Over time, China has evolved into the economy that produces significant value added, making it a crucial player in global production networks. This shift has led to China's consolidation of technologically advanced industries and services, thereby increasing its responsibility for high-value-added processes (Ambos et al., 2021; Xing, 2016).

The introduction of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) in 2013 and the Digital Silk Road two years later marked a clear indication of China's ambition to dominate technological GVCs (Hussain, 2023; Dekker et. al., 2020). As part of a long-term technology plan, Beijing has been supporting its exporters, including technology companies, and fostering technological cooperation with selected countries. These strategies have not only strengthened China's presence in the technological sphere but also increased the role of its products and services in GVCs. Furthermore, this strategy aligns with the ongoing fourth industrial revolution (Feliciano-Cestero et al., 2023; Lei, 2022; Kraus et al., 2022; Müller and Bulliga, 2019).

China has been a significant contributor to the value-added to GVCs. However, as the economy advances, Chinese services are expected to become an increasingly vital component in production networks. China is likely to promote advanced ICT services. Given the strained relations with the US and some Asian economies (e.g. Japan, Korea), Europe seems to be a key recipient of Chinese value-added flows from ICT services.

The study applies the concept of servicification of manufacturing by Miroudot and Cadestin (2017). It can be interpreted as using services in the manufacturing process in three stages: in intermediate consumption, production, and output. Services are involved in the production process as intermediate inputs, including packaging, marketing, and research and development. They also facilitate connections between manufacturing activities, such as logistics. Furthermore, they are integral to the product's sales and the after-sales services offered by companies (Miroudot, 2017).

The degree of servicification is measured as the percentage of services' value-added in manufacturing gross exports. Service inputs can either be from the domestic market or foreign countries, categorized as domestic or foreign servicification, respectively. By using the international input-output tables from 1995 to 2018 (Inter-Country Input-Output provided by the OECD), the degree of servicification across European countries (according to the OECD's classification) can be estimated.

The article attempts to answer the question: considering the increasing share of domestic services in China's manufacturing in recent years, is there a similar trend in Chinese services exported abroad and incorporated into foreign manufacturing (servicification of foreign manufacturing with Chinese value added), particularly European manufacturing? More specifically, is there also an increase in the share of Chinese services in the manufacturing of China's trading partners in Europe?

Europe was chosen in the article because the region is the second most important (after Southeast Asia) where Chinese manufacturing services are delivered. In 2018, Europe absorbed 1/4 of Chinese services supplied to global manufacturing (OECD, 2022). The focus on ICT services is explained in detail in the "Justification of the topic" section. ICT services are understood according to the OECD's classification and consist of publishing, audiovisual and broadcasting activities, telecommunications, and computer programming, consultancy, and information services activities.

The study consists of 31 European economies, perceived in geographical terms, (excluding Russia). If a specific group is taken into account, e.g. Western Europe or Central and Eastern Europe (CEE), then this is indicated in the text.

The paper is divided into five sections, including the introduction and conclusions. The "Literature review" introduces the concept of links between services and production. Then we justify the topic. It is followed by a brief description of the research method used in this paper. Section fourth examines the share of Chinese value added in European production in terms of ICT servicification of manufacturing. In the conclusions, the research questions and implications of the study are discussed.

2. Literature review

Though services seem to be an essential element in the global production and international trade of manufactured goods, limited research has been conducted on the role of services in GVCs. Many activities related to the manufacturing industries also require activities from non-manufacturing industries, such as services that are conducted domestically or imported from abroad. Unlike the "classical" approach, which emphasizes that manufacturing is only involved in the value added generated by manufacturing activities, with no connection to other industries' activities. The alternative approach focuses on the value added in all production stages of the manufacturing process. It means that production consists of the sum of many activities, including services, along the production chain that is used to produce the final

product, which implies that manufacturing consists of the sum of many activities (Timmer et al., 2012, 2014). Several authors refer to this process as servicification of manufacturing. Services are used throughout the manufacturing process in many ways. Typically, we apply them in the first stages of the value chain, such as R&D activities. We can also use them at the end of the chain, for instance, for maintenance or repair. In addition, we use a variety of services at every stage of production, such as IT services and telecommunications, which are also discussed in this paper.

The services industry has significantly contributed to economic growth, due to the recent advances in ICT. A variety of services have become more marketable thanks to technological advancement, digitalization and significant reductions in transportation costs. Moreover, automation has improved the labor-intensive manufacturing industries, and now services account for a much larger share of value added than manufacturing. In this literature review, we focused on studies from the last decade.

Links between manufacturing and services are included in the debate on deindustrialization (Juhasz et al., 2023; Gong et al., 2022; Rodrik, 2016) and the above-mentioned "servicification of manufacturing" (Atolia et al., 2028; National Board of Trade, 2012; Lodefalk, 2013).

Meckstroth (2017) demonstrated the practical application of Hirschman's unbalanced growth model, using a manufacturing plant as an example to explain the role of domestic services in the upstream supply chain, such as R&D services, outsourced professional services, transportation of inputs, and utilities. Gölgeci et al. (2021) discussed the servitization phenomenon in the context of GVCs and provided a conceptual framework for it. Pisano and Shih (2012) argued against separating manufacturing from services. Similarly, Eum and Lee (2022) argued that some upgrades in manufacturing are needed for different development paths.

While many studies have explored the significance of cross-sectoral relationships, most have not been international. For example, Chun et al. (2021) examined the shift in domestic employment composition due to the servicification of manufacturing in South Korea with foreign value added. Pattnayak and Chadha (2022) investigated whether service inputs could enhance the exports of manufacturing firms in India, a region known for its service industry. Reddy and Sasidharan (2022) conducted similar research. Rueda-Cantuche et al. (2012) discovered strong forward links from the financial sector to other areas of the EU economy. Hansen et al. (2022) studied servicification in South African firms and found it beneficial to focus on the role of services concerning GVC upgrades. Beverelli et al. (2016) also showed

strong links between domestic services and manufacturing, leading to a higher degree of GVCs integration, which they attributed to increased labor productivity and higher "value effects".

Participation in the global economy implies cross-sectoral overlaps on an international scale. However, the impact of services on manufacturing exports has not been extensively studied. A few studies have addressed this issue.

More than three decades ago, Hansen (1990) argued that by outsourcing and purchasing services, companies were able to improve their professional and technical level. Marshall et al. (1987) proved that using services, as intermediate inputs of the manufacturing industry, had positive effects on labor pool, knowledge spillover, and intermediate input sharing. Similar conclusions stem from Feng's (2009) studies. In turn, Wolfmayr (2012) analyzed OECD countries and found a significant positive effect of services on manufacturing competitiveness, particularly in international and business services and the most skill- and technology-intensive manufacturing. Miroudot and Cadestin (2017) reported that about 40% of the value-added in manufacturing firms across the OECD economies comes from services. Baldwin et al. (2015) found that the majority of manufacturing value added in Asia comes from services. Similar conclusions were drawn by Heuser and Matto (2017). Landesmann and Leitner (2015) found a positive effect on manufacturing competitiveness for both domestic and foreign intermediate business services in the EU. Díaz-Mora et al. (2018) examined the effect of foreign services' value-added included in manufacturing exports on export duration for 63 countries from 1995–2014 and found a positive effect, particularly in developing economies. Liu et al. (2018) found a positive effect of the development of financial and business services on the competitiveness of manufacturing exports, especially for manufacturing sectors that relied heavily on the services. Pezzotta et al. (2022) described the integration of traditional offers with digital services as "digital servitization". Verhoef et al. (2021) presented the stages of digital transformation, which included implementing ICT services. Moreover, many authors indicated ICT services as the most important factor of business development (e.g. Ramaswamy and Ozcan, 2016; Liu et al., 2016; Skare et al., 2023). Blázquez et al. (2020) investigated the phenomenon of international 'servicification' of manufacturing from 1995-2011 and found that services inputs are a key determining factor in manufacturing competitiveness. Similar conclusions were drawn by Kordalska and Olczyk (2021) analyzing links between services and manufacturing in CEE. Díaz-Mora et al. (2022) researched the impact of deep trade agreements on GVC-related services and found that deep trade agreements with services provisions increase embodied services' value-added from partner countries, with larger impacts for deeper agreements. Matthes and Kunkel (2020) investigated links between digitalization and

industrial policy, productivity, employment, sectoral linkages and trade in developing economies. Thangavelu et al. (2018) compared Asian economic connections in servicification with OECD countries.

When it comes to China's role in GVCs in terms of servicification, there has been only a small number of studies so far.

Ming-rong and Ming-xi (2009) provided one of the oldest studies. They empirically analyzed the relationship between producer services and the export of manufacturing enterprises in China in 2000-2007. They proved that services promoted the growth of export scale, profits and export transaction costs. Du and Agbola (2022) studied the servicification of manufacturing in China and found that FDI, capital intensity, and institutions are improving due to production links. However, they also observed that the increasing global market share of the Chinese manufacturing industry has led to a decrease in the role of manufacturing firms in China that use foreign servicification of manufacturing. Huang et al. (2022) and Chen et al. (2023) reached similar conclusions, demonstrating that the servicification of manufacturing, whether commercial or non-commercial, positively impacts the competitiveness of value-added exports and shapes the position of Chinese enterprises in the global network. They noted that the servicification of China's manufacturing sector is still in its early stages of development. Guo et al. (2018) built a model for the Chinese economy from 1981-2014 and conducted counterfactual experiments, highlighting the significant role of the servicification of investment. Zhang et al. (2023) study the heterogeneous impact of different types of servitization on firm performance in China. Chen et al. (2021, 2022) analyzed the telecom industry and how their services influenced industry growth and what innovations can boost its development (e.g. AI). Liu and Kim (2020) used an input-output model to determine that the service sector is a key driver for economic development. Zhang (2019) came to similar conclusions when analyzing the IT industry. Shen et al. (2021) went a similar path, using the textile industry in all provinces in China. Liao et al (2022) proved that there are some fixed configurations to realize GVCs transition in Chinese manufacturing enterprises, among which is industrial upgrading.

All these studies focused on the internal servicification of manufacturing and did not address international flows. There are only a few internationally oriented studies about China. Pomfret (2019) provided a case study on servicification as part of increased trade between China and Europe in the 20th century, using the Eurasian Landbridge Corridor as an example. Natanelov et al. (2022) found how advanced services (blockchain) could affect value chains. Yu et al. (2023) applied panel data from 44 countries and 18 industries spanning 14 years and

matched the global input–output database with micro-level data from Chinese manufacturing firms and found a positive effect of imported producer service inputs on domestic manufacturing exports.

The aforementioned studies have a few limitations. Firstly, they did not investigate all European countries) and their manufacturing sectors' reliance on Chinese services. Secondly, none of the studies concentrated on services related to high technology, specifically ICT. All of them focused on total services rather than classifying them according to their level of sophistication. Thirdly, previous research has focused on total servicification of manufacturing, in general, neglecting industry-specific analysis. This study aims to address these gaps and contributes to empirical studies in the field of cross-sectoral value-added flows.

2. Justification of the topic

The topic of servicification of European manufacturing with Chinese ICT stems from two issues: the gap in the literature which was presented above and the increasing role of services inputs in manufacturing.

Recent research (OECD 2022) (Liu and Li, 2022) (UNCTAD, 2023) underscores the significance of the servicification of manufacturing activities within the GVCs. At the same time, changes are being observed in Chinese output and inter-sectoral connections. Analyzing domestic output, it is noted that the share of services in manufacturing has increased significantly in recent years. At the same time, in final demand and gross exports, China is increasingly using domestic services in total output and manufacturing. This means that servicification of domestic manufacturing increased (figure 1). Moreover, ICT services play an important role in domestic manufacturing (figure 2). These tendencies might indicate that similar growth of servicification of manufacturing in terms of GVCs occurs too. These findings are consistent with the research conducted by Ming-rong and Ming-xi (2009), Du and Agbola (2022), Huang et al. (2022), Chen et al. (2023) and Guo et al. (2018).

Figure 1. Value-added flows to Chinese manufacturing in 1995 and 2018 (share of each sector contribution in total manufacturing output)

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, 2022.

Figure 2. Servicification of domestic manufacturing in China in 1995-2018 (share in total services embodied in domestic manufacturing)

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, 2022.

Within the realm of service trades, the significance of ICT service trade has been on the rise compared to other service types (UNCTAD, 2021). When it comes to Chinese technological strategies, ICT services are an important channel for influencing the production of other countries. ICT has become a crucial component of infrastructure connectivity due to its increasing use for connectivity purposes. ICT service import from China is expected to increase as a channel to achieve a higher ICT development, not only in less technologically advanced economies. Empirical analysis shows that China's export to its trade partners

(including Europe) has increased over the last decade, especially in capital-intensive industries (Yu et al., 2020). However, according to Melitz (2003), export decisions depend on the productivity of companies. Hence, as European economies become more technologically advanced, their ICT service firms are likely to see an increase in productivity for several reasons. Firstly, European firms can enhance their productivity by utilizing their new technology. Secondly, companies that are equipped with new technology are likely to have an increased ability to learn and absorb the technology and eventually maintain their productivity advantage (Cohen, Levinthal, 1990).

In 2022 the share of ICT services in all European services exports amounted to 15.6% (UNCTAD, 2023). In 2020, the value added by the EU's ICT sector was equivalent to 5.2% of GDP (Eurostat, 2023). On the other hand, we observe a decrease in domestic ICT services flows to European manufacturing (Figure 3). This implies growth in foreign ICT services flows, including Chinese services hypothetically. Ghodsi et al. (2021) carefully analyzed the condition of the ICT sector in Europe about the most important players in the market (e.g. U.S., China, India etc.). Their research found that Europe is no longer able to increase its capacity to create new jobs in ICT, unlike China. Gross output and value-added growth rates are also significantly below those in China. This may lead to the transfer of some manufacturing competencies by European companies to Chinese companies, which may result in increased inflows of Chinese value added from ICT services, and thus greater shares of China among the suppliers of such value added. Therefore, ICT flows from China to Europe seem to be important in the context of GVCs.

3. Description of the data and general study procedure

To determine the participation and status of the analyzed economies in GVCs, as well as the flows of value added between Chinese services and European manufacturing, a value-added model was developed. It included value added in industries/sectors. The Leontief input-output model was used as a basic approach. The balance equations system in the input-output model for a single economy was modified to suit a multi-economy model. This model is grounded on the decomposition of gross exports. Then it was developed by several authors: (Timmer et al., 2012) (Johnson and Noguera, 2012) (Koopman et al., 2014). The method not only provides estimates of total value added in GVCs, but also performs calculations at the mezo-economic level and cross-sectoral flows of value added, including the servicification of manufacturing.

In our approach, these models were extended to sector/industry analyses, as far as statistical data permitted. Value-added statistics are collected by the OECD's Inter-Country Input-Output (ICIO) Database, which contains data up to 2018. We collected the data and created an index of foreign value added embodied in a country's gross exports, which helps us determine the extent to which a country is dependent on the global/certain state's production network. In our paper, we classified ICT services according to the OECD's ISIC Revision 4. The input-output model for the breakdown of gross exports was utilized to assess the intersectoral connections among economies.

The methodology is predicated on the premise that within each economy, there exist S sectors/industries encompassing N economies. Each sector/industry is dedicated to the production of a distinct differentiated good. Production serves the dual purpose of satisfying final demand and generating intermediate goods (semi-finished products), which subsequently find utility in subsequent stages of product fabrication, both domestically and internationally.

$$X_i(s) = \sum_j y_{ij}(s) + \sum_j \sum_t z_{ij}(s, t),$$

where we define the coefficients matrix A as a matrix of dimension $SN \times SN$, with elements

$$a_{ij}(s, t) = z_{ij}(s, t) / x_j(t)$$

Thus, the basic condition was formulated

$$x = (I - A)^{-1}y$$

Which can be represented in the form of the following matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} X_1 \\ \vdots \\ X_N \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} I - A_{11} & \cdots & -A_{1N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ -A_{N1} & \cdots & I - A_{NN} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \sum_i^N Y_{1j} \\ \vdots \\ \sum_i^N Y_{Nj} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Z_{11} & \cdots & Z_{1N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ Z_{N1} & \cdots & Z_{NN} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} Y_1 \\ \vdots \\ Y_N \end{bmatrix}$$

The matrix can be transformed into the following input-output model:

$$\begin{bmatrix} X_{11} & \cdots & X_{1N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ X_{N1} & \cdots & X_{NN} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Z_{11} & \cdots & Z_{1N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ Z_{N1} & \cdots & Z_{NN} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} Y_{11} & \cdots & Y_{1N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ Y_{N1} & \cdots & Y_{NN} \end{bmatrix}$$

Where, in this model, there are N countries and S sectors. In this context, Z represents an $SN \times SN$ matrix, while X and Y are $SN \times N$ matrices.

Z - means gross production in the i economy that is needed to meet the final demand in the economy j

X - output produced in the i country that is absorbed by the market of country j

Y - output produced in the i country that is consumed by the country j

A value-added production matrix $\widehat{V}\widehat{V}ZY$ was then formulated

$$\begin{bmatrix} \widehat{V}_1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \cdots & \widehat{V}_N \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X_{11} & \cdots & X_{1N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ X_{N1} & \cdots & X_{NN} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \widehat{V}_1 \sum_j^N Z_{1j} Y_{j1} & \cdots & \widehat{V}_1 \sum_j^N Z_{1j} Y_{jN} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \widehat{V}_N \sum_j^N Z_{Nj} Y_{j1} & \cdots & \widehat{V}_N \sum_j^N Z_{Nj} Y_{jN} \end{bmatrix}$$

The diagonal matrix represents the value added of production that has been retained within the country, whereas the elements outside the diagonal matrix represent the value added that has been absorbed by the rest of the world (value added embodied in the gross exports of the trading partner).

$$VAExports_i = \sum_{j \neq i}^N V X_{ij} = V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N \sum_{n=1}^N Z_{in} Y_{nj} = V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ii} Y_{ij} + V_i \sum_{j \neq 1}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jj} + V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N \sum_{t \neq ij}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jt}$$

Where:

$V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ii} Y_{ij}$ is the value added embodied in gross exports of final goods

$V_i \sum_{j \neq 1}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jj}$ is the value added embodied in gross exports of intermediate goods (semi-finished products)

$V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N \sum_{t \neq ij}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jt}$ is indirect value added embodied in gross exports.

In order to formulate the share of value added coming from abroad in the gross export of the analyzed country, the following notation must be used:

$$VS = \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_j Z_{ji} E_{i*} = \sum_{t \neq i}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} Y_{ij} + \sum_{t \neq i}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} A_{ij} (I - A_{jj})^{-1} Y_{jj} + \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} (I - A_{jj})^{-1} E_{j*}$$

Where:

$\sum_{t \neq i}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} Y_{ij}$ – is foreign value added included in gross exports of final goods

$\sum_{t \neq i}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} A_{ij} (I - A_{jj})^{-1} Y_{jj}$ – is foreign value added included in gross exports of intermediate goods

$\sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} (I - A_{jj})^{-1} E_{j*}$ - is the double-calculated value added of intermediate goods produced abroad.

Finally, the export of intermediate goods that is used as an input to the production of goods abroad can be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{VSI} &= V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ji} E_{i*} = V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jt} + V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} A_{ij} A_{jt} X_t + \\ &V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jt} + V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} A_{ji} X_i \end{aligned}$$

Where:

$V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jt}$ – is indirect value added embodied in gross exports.

$V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} A_{ij} A_{jt} X_t$ – is the export of intermediate goods that will be used abroad to produce gross exports of intermediate goods

$V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} Y_{ji}$ – is domestic value added that returns to the country in the form of final products

$V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} A_{ji} X_i$ – is the domestic value added returned through imports of intermediate goods

Finally, the decomposition of gross exports can be formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DCP} &= [V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ii} Y_{ij} + V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jj} + V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N \sum_{t \neq ij}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jt}] + [\sum_{t \neq i}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} Y_{ij} + \\ &\sum_{t \neq i}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} A_{ij} (I - A_{jj})^{-1} Y_{jj} + \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} (I - A_{jj})^{-1} E_{j*}] + [V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} Y_{ji} + \\ &V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} A_{ji} (I - A_{ii})^{-1} Y_{ii} + V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} A_{jt} (I - A_{ii})^{-1} E_{i*} \end{aligned}$$

The above formulas can be explained as follows:

$$V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} Y_{ij} + V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jj} + V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N \sum_{t \neq ij}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jt} \quad \text{and} \quad V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} Y_{ji} + V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} A_{ji} (I - A_{ii})^{-1} Y_{ii} + V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} A_{jt} (I - A_{ii})^{-1} E_{i*} - \text{domestic value added embodied in the trading partner's gross exports (IVA)}$$

$$\sum_{t \neq i}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} Y_{ij} + \sum_{t \neq i}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} A_{ij} (I - A_{jj})^{-1} Y_{jj} + \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} (I - A_{jj})^{-1} E_{j*} - \text{foreign value added embodied in a country's gross exports (FVA)}$$

The formulas provided for calculating domestic value added embodied in the gross exports of partner countries and foreign value added embodied in the gross exports of the country also facilitate the assessment of the country's connections with foreign nations. In this context, the first formula represents the forward linkages or forward participation in GVCs, while the second formula can be associated with the backward linkages or participation. This study focuses on foreign value added.

4. Results

4.1. General tendencies

Analyzing the trend of the shares of Chinese services in Europe's manufacturing (also divided into Western Europe and CEE), we can observe that they did not decrease in any economy between 1995-1999 and 2015-2018. However, only ICT services recorded a slight decline in the period 2010-2014, after which they returned to the growth path. This decline was caused by the deteriorating atmosphere around China (related to China's active involvement in investing billions of euros in Portuguese and Greek bonds) and the introduction of regulations targeting Chinese technology and protecting European companies from technology takeover by the Chinese. Another interesting phenomenon appears - in the case of ICT services, the largest gap in servitization is observed between Western Europe and CEE. In other cases, China's shares are quite balanced. This is probably due to the higher advancement of manufacturing in Western Europe (due to the introduction of strategies related to Industry 4.0) and the greater absorption of advanced services by manufacturing in general (including Chinese). However, the CEE countries were characterized by lower manufacturing advancement and hence the absorption of services enriching manufacturing was lower.

Table 1. Chinese servicification of European manufacturing in 1995-2018 (%)

	Europe					Western Europe					CEE				
	1995-1999	2000-2004	2005-2009	2010-2014	2015-2018	1995-1999	2000-2004	2005-2009	2010-2014	2015-2018	1995-1999	2000-2004	2005-2009	2010-2014	2015-2018
Distributive trade transport, accommodation and food services	3.0	5.6	10.2	13.6	16.8	2.3	3.9	6.5	8.3	10.7	0.8	2.5	4.5	6.4	7.8
Information and communication	3.1	4.1	6.0	5.4	7.9	2.6	3.3	4.5	4.2	6.4	0.9	2.0	3.4	3.0	3.9
Financial and insurance activities	3.5	4.8	11.2	17.6	19.0	2.7	3.6	8.1	12.5	14.6	1.2	2.8	7.7	12.2	15.3
Other business sector services	1.9	2.5	4.2	6.4	7.5	1.6	2.0	3.2	4.7	5.8	0.5	1.0	1.9	3.4	4.3
Total services	2.8	4.6	8.3	11.3	13.4	2.3	3.4	5.6	7.4	9.3	0.8	2.0	4.0	5.8	7.1

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, 2022.

Meanwhile, when looking for manufacturing industries with the highest shares of Chinese ICT services in 2018, which will be analyzed in more detail later in the article, the following are indicated: chemicals and non-metallic mineral products, computer, electronic and electrical equipment industry and transport equipment industry (Table 2). The chemicals and non-metallic mineral products were characterized by the largest increase in shares since 1995. However, most industries recorded a decline in shares. This is related to the increased intensification of Chinese ICT inflows into European business services (OECD, 2022).

Table 2. Chinese ICT services in European manufacturing by industry in 1995 and 2018 (share in total ICT services flows to manufacturing)

Industry		1995	2018	
D10T33: Manufacturing		63.1%	50.9%	
D10T33: Manufacturing	D10T12: Food products, beverages and tobacco	2.8%	2.2%	
	D13T15: Textiles, wearing apparel, leather and related products	4.7%	1.1%	
	D16T18: Wood and paper products and printing	1.4%	1.3%	
	D16T18: Wood and paper products and printing	D16: Wood and products of wood and cork	0.3%	0.3%
		D17T18: Paper products and printing	1.1%	1.0%
	D19T23: Chemicals and non-metallic mineral products		11.9%	11.0%
		D19: Coke and refined petroleum products	1.4%	1.4%
	D20T21: Chemicals and pharmaceutical products	8.3%	8.0%	

D19T23: Chemicals and non-metallic mineral products	D20T21: Chemicals and pharmaceutical products	D20: Chemical and chemical products	6.4%	4.4%
		D21: Pharmaceuticals, medicinal chemical and botanical products	1.9%	3.7%
	D22: Rubber and plastics products		1.4%	1.1%
	D23: Other non-metallic mineral products		0.9%	0.5%
D24T25: Basic metals and fabricated metal products			6.0%	3.7%
D24T25: Basic metals and fabricated metal products	D24: Basic metals		3.7%	2.1%
	D25: Fabricated metal products		2.3%	1.6%
D26T27: Computer, electronic and electrical equipment			11.3%	10.9%
D26T27: Computer, electronic and electrical equipment	D26: Computer, electronic and optical products		7.6%	7.3%
	D27: Electrical equipment		3.7%	3.5%
D28: Machinery and equipment n.e.c			11.9%	8.3%
D29T30: Transport equipment			10.2%	10.3%
D29T30: Transport equipment	D29: Motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers		6.7%	6.7%
	D30: Other transport equipment		3.4%	3.6%
D31T33: Manufacturing nec; repair and installation of machinery and equipment			2.9%	2.0%

The sum of the percentages of the main groups is less than 100% because the table does not include non-manufacturing industries.

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, 2022.

4.2. Trends in servicification of manufacturing with ICT

4.2.1. Servicification of total manufacturing

When analyzing European economies in the concept of servicification of manufacturing with ICT services in 1995-2018, we observed that all economies increased their dependence on Chinese ICT services. For most of the period under review, Western Europe outperformed CEE in the inflows of Chinese ICT services. However, the gap between these regions is starting to narrow. During this period, Czechia, Hungary and Germany noted the largest share of Chinese ICT services inflows to their manufacturing. In 2018, the largest shares were observed in Finland and Germany (5.9% each) and Estonia (5.8%). These economies were characterized also by the largest share of Chinese ICT in their manufacturing in 2015-2018. It is worth adding, that in 1995-1999 Germany and Finland were also the largest recipients of Chinese ICT (Table 3). Increasing the use of Chinese value added from ICT in manufacturing occurred with varying intensity. During the whole research period, the largest increases were observed in Estonia (5.3%), followed by Finland (4.9%) and Czechia (4.5%) (Table A in appendix).

Table 3. Servicification of European manufacturing with Chinese ICT services in 1995-2018
(% of gross exports)

	1995-1999	2000-2004	2005-2009	2010-2014	2015-2018	1995-2012	2013-2018
Austria	0.60	0.86	1.34	1.52	2.60	1.01	2.30
Belgium	0.80	0.94	1.42	1.04	1.60	1.04	1.43
Czechia	0.72	1.62	3.60	3.54	4.18	2.29	3.82
Denmark	0.90	1.36	1.64	2.18	3.88	1.41	3.42
Estonia	0.60	1.52	2.36	2.90	4.60	1.71	4.08
Finland	1.38	1.28	2.62	2.60	4.65	1.87	4.05
France	1.12	1.60	2.42	2.44	3.75	1.81	3.38
Germany	1.64	1.66	2.48	2.76	4.70	2.03	4.15
Greece	1.18	1.88	1.98	1.94	3.43	1.71	2.97
Hungary	0.76	2.48	3.80	2.80	3.35	2.46	3.05
Iceland	0.62	1.58	1.62	1.78	2.78	1.33	2.53
Ireland	0.50	0.82	1.56	0.60	0.88	0.89	0.80
Italy	0.92	1.50	2.16	2.16	3.28	1.62	2.95
Latvia	0.66	0.98	1.48	1.70	2.98	1.12	2.63
Lithuania	0.58	1.28	1.28	1.52	2.15	1.15	1.87
Luxembourg	1.12	1.12	1.32	1.20	2.00	1.18	1.77
Netherlands	0.68	1.14	1.50	1.68	3.05	1.19	2.63
Norway	0.78	1.28	1.70	1.78	3.23	1.31	2.83
Poland	0.98	1.48	2.46	2.26	3.50	1.73	3.12
Portugal	0.62	0.84	1.26	1.20	2.08	0.94	1.82
Slovakia	0.96	1.28	2.74	2.70	3.78	1.81	3.48
Slovenia	0.68	1.04	1.52	1.52	2.53	1.14	2.23
Spain	0.96	1.52	2.28	2.12	3.53	1.66	3.12
Sweden	0.84	1.06	1.40	2.32	4.33	1.22	3.90
Switzerland	0.72	1.20	1.60	1.58	2.90	1.21	2.55
United Kingdom	1.24	1.86	2.30	1.94	2.98	1.81	2.68
Bulgaria	0.72	1.04	1.98	1.36	2.35	1.25	2.07
Croatia	0.54	0.98	1.80	1.46	1.90	1.17	1.73
Cyprus	1.14	1.98	1.88	1.62	2.48	1.65	2.22
Malta	0.90	1.46	1.42	1.48	2.40	1.27	2.17
Romania	0.72	1.18	1.78	1.40	2.20	1.25	1.95
Europe	0.86	1.35	1.96	1.91	3.03	1.46	2.70
Western Europe	0.93	1.31	1.85	1.85	3.11	1.42	2.76
CEE	0.69	1.30	1.97	1.85	2.68	1.41	2.41

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, 2022.

Following CEE's accession to the EU, there was no shift of Chinese ICT in manufacturing from Western European economies to CEE. While some CEE economies, such as Estonia, have specialized more in advanced services and have begun to attract a significant amount of ICT services from China, most CEE economies have struggled to transition towards more advanced GVCs (Di Bernardino and Onesti, 2020).

A growing trend was observed in most European economies (except for Czechia, Hungary, and Croatia; however, these drops were insignificant) in servicification of manufacturing with

Chinese ICT. Between 1995 and 2018, the median increased from 0.8% to 3.7%. The median for Western Europe was 3.9%, while CEE's median amounted to 3.2% (in 1995 these medians were 0.9% and 0.6% respectively). The lowest reliance on Chinese ICT services was observed in Ireland (1.0%), while the greatest – in Germany and Finland (5.9%) (Figure 4, Table A in appendix).

Figure 4. Servicification of European manufacturing with Chinese ICT in 1995 and 2018 (% of gross exports)

1995

2018

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, 2022.

Taking into account the share of Chinese ICT in European countries' manufacturing, it can be seen that by 2012 it was 1.46%, compared to 2.70% in 2013-2018. This could be interpreted as an influence of the BRI introduction. However, such statements should be made with caution, as these increases may have been dictated by the generally increasing trends of servicification with foreign services in these countries. When we analyze individual economies, almost all, except for Ireland, noted an increase in China's share in the servicification of manufacturing with ICT services. When we compare the changes in servicification of manufacturing before and after the BRI it is difficult to identify any common trends. Only 1/3 of analyzed economies (mostly from Western Europe) were characterized by the above-average increases in both analyzed periods. At the same time, these are mostly countries that are most dependent on Chinese ICT services. Another 1/3 of economies were characterized by below-average increases in analyzed periods, but most of them relied very little on Chinese value added. In the period 1995-2012, the shares of Chinese ICT services in European manufacturing were more balanced; the standard deviation of Chinese shares was 0.7%. However, since 2013 it has increased to 1.1%. Economies have emerged with strong ties to Chinese value-added, while some economies have only slightly increased their dependence on China (Figure 5). Analyzing Chinese FDI going to Europe and comparing it with the inflows of value added (not only in the context of ICT services), it is also difficult to draw a clear conclusion. No significant changes were observed after the introduction of the BRI (even in countries belonging to the

'17+1' format), and the intensity of inflows depended more on bilateral relations than on multilateral agreements. Only for the first 3 years after the introduction of BRI and the inclusion of CEE countries in the '17+1' formula, increases in Chinese FDI were observed. However, FDI inflows returned to previous patterns - the most important FDI recipients were Germany, France and the UK. Since 2017 (due to the deteriorating political atmosphere around China and the start of the US-China trade war), declines in Chinese FDI have been observed in Europe, which does not translate into declines in the inflow of value added to gross exports. Moreover, the sectoral structure of these FDIs has changed - from FDI focused on infrastructure, finance and energy, China has moved towards FDI in the automotive and consumption sectors, which may intensify the absorption of value added (Rhodium Group, 2023).

Figure 5. Changes in servicification of European countries manufacturing with Chinese ICT services in 1995-2018 (% of gross exports)

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, 2022.

The article discusses the issue of servicification from China to Europe, and not the other way around due to the low shares of European countries in Chinese manufacturing. In 1995, the median for Western European services used in Chinese manufacturing amounted to 0.6%, while the clear outliers were Germany (3.80%) and the UK (3%). CEE did not count at all as a supplier of value-added (Table A in appendix). By 2018, the situation had improved slightly.

The median for Western Europe rose to 1%, with Germany and the UK still the outliers (7.6% and 4.1% respectively). CEE still played a marginal role (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Servicing of Chinese manufacturing with European ICT in 1995 and 2018 (% of gross exports)

1995

2018

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, 2022.

Generally, the intensity of the influx of Chinese ICT services to European manufacturing resulted from the confluence of several factors favorable for China: the debt crisis in the eurozone, the fall in the euro exchange rate and deindustrialization processes in Europe (especially Western Europe). At that time, China's internationalization and economic advancement strategies involving the acquisition of technology companies in developed countries strongly intensified. Hence, it can be concluded that the inflows of Chinese value added from ICT could be also related to Chinese investments and trade with Europe (Rhodium Group, 2023).

When analyzing value added flows between Europe and China, it is important to look at the gaps between these flows. China's ICT value added increased in Germany, the UK, France and some CEE economies significantly. Despite this, still, the role of the European value added in ICT is much larger than the role of Chinese ICT services in European manufacturing. Generally, comparing the manufacturing dependence of Western Europe and CEE on Chinese ICT services, a convergence can be seen. Although there are some outliers, both regions are becoming increasingly and similarly dependent on Chinese value added. There is a large asymmetry between the Western Europe and China flows. However, this gap is narrowing gradually. Unfortunately, this symptom is not visible in the CEE flows to China. CEE's ICT

services have a minor share in Chinese manufacturing and show no improvement over the years (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Changes in servicification of European manufacturing with Chinese ICT and Chinese manufacturing with European ICT in 1995-2018 (% of destination region’s gross exports)

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, 2022.

Figure 8 illustrates the development of forward link networks between China and European economies in 1995 and 2018. These links mean flows of domestic value added embodied in trade partners' gross exports Timmer et al. (2012). In 1995, Germany was the hub for all forward links in the network, with stronger regional value chains in Western Europe than in CEE. China's role was limited, supporting only a few Western European economies like Germany and the UK. The CEE economies lacked strong regional connections and links to China, with their strongest connections being with Germany. By 2018, these forward linkages had strengthened for both Western and CEE economies and China. Germany remained the regional hub, but CEE's and China's role had significantly increased.

Figure 8. Forward linkages between China and European economies in servicification of manufacturing with ICT (years 1995 and 2018)

Domestic value added in foreign exports as a share of gross exports, by foreign exporting country. It is calculated according to the methodology proposed by Koopman et al. (2010) and Timmer et al. (2012).

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, 2022.

4.2.2. Servicification of selected industries

The chemicals and non-metallic mineral products, computer, electronic and electrical equipment industry and transport equipment industry were absorbing Chinese ICT services particularly intensively (Table 2).

In the case of servicification of European chemicals and non-metallic mineral products with Chinese ICT between 1995 and 2018, significant increases were observed (the median

increased from 0.65% to 2.90%). Both, in 1995 and 2018, the median share of Western Europe exceeded CEE, however, the advantage was not so large (0.90% to 0.60% in 1995 and 3.50% to 2.70% in 2018). The shares of Chinese ICT's value added in this sector were lower than in the next described industries. Europe relied more on value added from the US, Russian Federation or India than on China. In 2018, the largest share of Chinese ICT services was directed to Germany (in 1995 Germany was also an outlier) and Denmark. These shares in CEE, the largest shares (however much lower than in Western Europe) were absorbed by Estonia and the Czechia (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Servicification of European chemicals and non-metallic mineral products industry with Chinese ICT in 1995 and 2018 (% of gross exports)

1995

2018

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, 2022.

In the case of the servicification of the European computer, electronic and electrical equipment industry with Chinese ICT between 1995 and 2018, significant increases were observed (the median increased from 0.78% to 5.56%). Both, in 1995 and 2018, the share of Western Europe significantly exceeds CEE (median amounted to 0.89% and 0.60% in 1995 respectively and in 2018 amounted to 5.73% and 4.63%) (Figure 10). This is related to the aforementioned increased Chinese FDI in Western European technologies. In terms of the share of Chinese ICT services in the analyzed industry, among foreign value-added recipients in Europe, the first places were taken by: Czechia (9.9%), Estonia (9.3%), Slovakia (8.9%) and Germany (8.4%). It should be noted that in the case of Czechia, this share decreased (from a maximum of 11% in 2010) (Table A in appendix). The high share of Chinese ICT services in Czech electronics should be explained not by Chinese FDI in this country, but by a certain specificity of the Czech electronics industry. It is characterized by a large number of imported materials, components and parts for production and assembly. Almost $\frac{3}{4}$ of exports are made by imported components.

Figure 10. Servicification of European computer, electronic and electrical equipment industry with Chinese ICT in 1995 and 2018 (% of gross exports)

1995

2018

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, 2022.

From 1995 to 2018, the European transport equipment industry experienced a significant rise in the integration with Chinese ICT services. The median increased from 0.70% to 3.57% (Figure 11). Western Europe had a larger share than CEE, but the gap is gradually narrowing. The transport equipment industry is less reliant on Chinese ICT compared to the computer, electronic, and electrical equipment industry. However, this could change as China is showing a keen interest in the global automotive industry, investing heavily in Europe and developing its industry. The largest recipients of Chinese ICT services are automotive powerhouses like Germany, France, Spain, and Sweden. In 2018, Germany led the way, accounting for 83% of the value added in the EU-28 in this sector. Greece (5.6%), Finland, and Germany (5.4% each) had the highest shares of Chinese ICT services in their industries in 2018 (Table A in appendix). The high share in Greece is attributed to maritime equipment. Despite a negligible role in the past, Greece's share has grown rapidly after China's takeover of the port of Piraeus and significant FDI. While Western Europe still has a higher median, CEE's role in Chinese ICT services is on the rise.

Figure 11. Servicification of European transport equipment industry with Chinese ICT in 1995 and 2018 (% of gross exports)

1995

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, 2022.

Conclusions

The role of the Chinese economy in GVCs is strengthening and transforming. Currently, Chinese companies are moving towards services and business model improvements and focusing on digitalization (Chen et al., 2021, 2022; Zhang, 2019). A symptom of this novelty is the form of production servicing, which is expected to change the GVC landscape. By introducing various strategies to stimulate technological development, China has increasingly focused on the export of value added from advanced technologies, including ICT services. The largest recipients of these services are the countries of Southeast Asia and, analyzed in the article, the European countries.

The inflows of Chinese ICT services to European manufacturing presented in the article show China's consistent strategy related to increasing its influence in the production of developed economies. Particularly visible is the focus of ICT service streams on industries that are key to China's development - computer, electronic and electrical equipment industry, and more recently, chemicals and non-metallic mineral products and transport equipment industry. However, it is difficult to say whether this trend will continue, given the current situation in the global economy and China's limited access to modern technologies.

Referring to the research question regarding the growing share of Chinese services exported abroad and incorporated into European production, it is difficult to deny this trend. Both in individual European economies and divided into Western Europe and CEE, the shares of Chinese services are growing. The results of this study are consistent with the analyses conducted by Pomfret (2019) and Yu et al. (2023). Moreover, when analyzing in detail ICT services that are an expression of China's upgrade in GVCs, a growing trend can also be noticed. The increases in the shares of Chinese ICT services are particularly visible in the last years of the research period. Moreover, research on the shares of Chinese ICT services in manufacturing industries allowed us to find key European industries in which the Chinese are particularly interested. The study showed that computer, electronic and electrical equipment and the transport equipment industries absorb the most of Chinese services.

The study also revealed a significant asymmetry in the flow of ICT services between China and Europe. In the case of Western Europe, this gap is slowly closing, which is confirmed by the increasing openness of both markets to each other's services and the simultaneous intensification of the inflow of ICT services from China. In the case of China-CEE flows, there is still a high asymmetry and no signs of closing the gap. This means that companies from the CEE region do not massively export ICT services to the Chinese market because they either do not produce them and/or they are not service providers that can face the competition from Western European companies. However, the intense growth in the share of Chinese ICT services in manufacturing in CEE confirms the high demand for these services, which may still indicate poor development of the internal market for these services.

These results may constitute the basis for negotiations with China regarding broader and preferential admission of CEE suppliers to the market to reduce this asymmetry. The study also highlighted European industries that are particularly vulnerable to this asymmetry.

Ultimately, we should be aware of some limitations in the study's findings. Firstly, the COVID-19 pandemic and now the war in Ukraine have changed the landscape of production networks, which should be considered carefully, as new data is still being gathered. Secondly, there is the danger that Europe decouples from Chinese technology. The first indication of this phenomenon was the freezing of the Comprehensive Investment Agreement's ratification. Finally, limitations of the study may result from the specifically adopted methodology and statistical data. There are alternative methods (e.g. Mancini; Tsigas et al., 2012) and data (The World Input-Output Database or Global Trade Analysis Project database) that could give slightly different results.

References

1. Ambos, B., Brandl, K., Perri, A., Scalera, V.G., Van Assche, A. (2021), The nature of innovation in global value chains, *Journal of World Business*, 56(4).
2. Atolia, M., Loungani, P., Marquis, M., & Papageorgiou, C. (2018). Rethinking Development Policy: Deindustrialization, Servicification and Structural Transformation. *IMF Working Papers*, 18(223), 1. <https://doi.org/10.5089/9781484377499.001>
3. Baldwin, R.; Forslid, R.; Ito, T. (2015), Unveiling the Evolving Sources of Value Added in Exports; IDE-JETRO Joint Research Program Series: Chiba, Japan, 2015.
4. Belotti, F., Borin, A., Mancini, M. (2020), Economic Analysis with Inter-Country Input-Output Tables in Stata, World Development Report 2020, Background Paper.
5. Beverelli, C.; Koopman, R.; Kummritz, V.; Neumueller, S. (2016) Domestic Foundations of Global Value Chains. Available online: <http://pubdocs.worldbank.org/en/953701480958600245/2-BEVERELLI-paper.pdf>.
6. Blázquez, L.; Diaz-Mora, C.; González-Díaz, B. (2020), The role of services content for manufacturing competitiveness: A network analysis. *PLoS ONE*.
7. Chen, G., Liu, Y., Gao, Q., Zhang, J. (2023). Does regional services development enhance manufacturing firm productivity? A manufacturing servitization perspective, *International Review of Economics and Finance*, 86, 451-466.
8. Chen, H., Li, L., & Chen, Y. (2021). Explore success factors that impact artificial intelligence adoption on telecom industry in China. *Journal of Management Analytics*, 8(1), 36-68.
9. Chen, H., Li, L., & Chen, Y. (2022). Sustainable growth research—A study on the telecom operators in China. *Journal of Management Analytics*, 9(1), 17-31.
10. Chun, H., Hur, J., & Son, N. S. (2021). Global value chains and servicification of manufacturing: Evidence from firm-level data. *Japan and the World Economy*, 58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.japwor.2021.101074>.
11. Cohen, W.M., Levinthal, D.A., (1990), Absorptive capacity: A new perspective on learning and innovation, *Administrative Science Quarterly*, pp. 128-152
12. Dekker, B., Okano-Heijmans, M., Zhang, E.S. (2020), Unpacking China's DSR, Clingendael Report.
13. Di Bernardino, C., & Onesti, O. (2020). Explaining deindustrialisation from a vertical perspective: Industrial linkages, producer services, and international trade”, *Economics and New Technology*, online first.

14. Díaz-Mora, C., García-López, E., & González-Díaz, B. (2022). Bilateral servicification in global value chains and deep trade agreements. *World Economy*, 45(8), 2510–2531. <https://doi.org/10.1111/twec.13246>
15. Díaz-Mora, C.; Gandoy, R.; Gonzalez-Díaz, B. (2018) Strengthening the stability of exports through GVC participation: The who and how matters. *J. Econ. Stud.*, 45, 610–637.
16. Du, Y., & Agbola, F. W. (2022). Servicification and global value chain upgrading: empirical evidence from China’s manufacturing industry. *Journal of the Asia Pacific Economy*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13547860.2022.2049526>
17. E. Biewen, D. Harsch, J. Spies (2012), The determinants of service imports: The role of cost pressure and financial constraints, Deutsche Bundesbank, Discussion Paper.
18. Eum, W., Lee, J.-D. (2022), Alternative paths of diversification for developing countries, *Review of Development Economics*, 26(4).
19. Feliciano-Cestero, M.M., Ameen, N., Kotabe, M., Paul, J., Signoret, M. (2023), Is digital transformation threatened? A systematic literature review of the factors influencing firms’ digital transformation and internationalization, *Journal of Business Research*, 157.
20. Feng, T.-W. (2009), The Relationship between Producer Service and Manufacturing Efficiency. *J. Quant. Tech. Econ.*, 3, 56–65.
21. Foster-McGregor, N.; Pöschl, J.; Stehrer, R. (2012) Manufacturing Productivity: Effects of Service Sector Innovations and Institutions; wiiw Working Paper: Vienna, Austria, No. 89.; Available online: <https://wiiw.ac.at/manufacturing-productivity-effects-of-service-sector-innovations-and-institutions-dlp-2759.pdf#:~:text=Manufacturing%20productivity%3A%20effects%20of%20service%20sector%20innovations%20and,countries.%20The%20importance%20of%20this%20question%20is%20evident.>
22. Ghodsi, M., Adarov, A., Exadaktylos, D., Stehrer, R., Stöllinger, R. (2021), Production and trade of ICT from an EU perspective, wiiw Research Report No. 456.
23. Gölgeci, I., Gligor, D.M., Lacka, E. and Raja, J.Z. (2021), Understanding the influence of servitization on global value chains: a conceptual framework, *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, Vol. 41 No. 5, pp. 645-667.
24. Gong, H., Hassink, R., Foster, C., Hess, M., Garretsen, H. (2022), *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society*, 15(2), 165–181.

25. Grimes, S. & Sun, J. (2014), Implications of China's on-going dependence on foreign technology. *Geoforum*. 54, 59-69.
26. Guo, K., Hang, J., & Yan, S. (2018). Servicification of Investment and Structural Transformation: The Case of China. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3061631>
27. Hansen, N. (1990), Do Producer Services Induce Regional Economic Development?, *Journal of Regional Science*, 30, 465–476.
28. Hansen, U. E., Nygaard, I., Morris, M., & Robbins, G. (2022). Servicification of Manufacturing in Global Value Chains: Upgrading of Local Suppliers of Embedded Services in the South African Market for Wind Turbines. *Journal of Development Studies*, 58(4), 787–808. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220388.2021.2017892>
29. Heuser, C., Mattoo, A. (2017), Services Trade and Global Value Chains, World Bank Policy Research Working Paper No. 8126, <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3006200>
30. Huang, G., Ma, L., Ziguang X., (2022). Servitization of Manufacturing and China's Power Status Upgrading of Global Value Network. SSRN, <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4079780>.
31. Hussain, F., Hussain, Z., Khan, M. I., & Imran, A. (2023). The digital rise and its economic implications for China through the Digital Silk Road under the Belt and Road Initiative. *Asian Journal of Comparative Politics*, online first.
32. Johnson, R.C.; Noguera, G. (2012), Proximity and Production Fragmentation. *Am. Econ. Rev.*, 102, 407–411.
33. Juhász, R., Lane, N.J., Rodrik, D. (2023), The New Economics of Industrial Policy, NBER Working Paper, 31538, <https://www.nber.org/papers/w31538>.
34. Koopman, R., W. Powers, Z. Wang and S.-J. Wei (2010), Give Credit Where Credit Is Due: Tracing Value Added in Global Production Chains”, NBER Working Paper, No. 16426.
35. Koopman, R.; Wang, Z.; Wei, S.-J. (2014) Tracing Value-added and Double Counting in Gross Exports. *Am. Econ. Rev.*, 104, 459–494.
36. Kordalska, A., Olczyk, M. (2021), Linkages between services and manufacturing as a new channel for GVC development: Evidence from CEE countries, *Structural Change and Economic Dynamics*, 58.
37. Kraus, S., Durst, S., Ferreira, J.J., Veiga, P., Kailer, N., Weinmann, A. (2022). Digital transformation in business and management research: An overview of the current status quo, *International Journal of Information Management*, 63.

38. Kwan, T. & Ryou, J.W. (2015), Global Value Chains of East Asia: Trade in Value Added and Vertical Specialization. *Asian Economic Journal*. 29(2), 121-143.
39. Landesmann, M.; Leitner, S.M. (2015) Labour Mobility of Migrants and Natives in the European Union: An Empirical Test of the ‘Greasing of the Wheel-Effect’ of Migrants; Vienna Institute for International Economic Studies (wiiw): Vienna, Austria. Working Paper 119.. Available online: <https://wiiw.ac.at/labour-mobility-of-migrants-and-natives-in-the-european-union-an-empirical-test-of-the-greasing-of-the-wheels-effect-of-migrants-dlp-3670.pdf>.
40. Lanz, R., & Maurer, A. (2015). Services and Global Value Chains: Servicification of Manufacturing and Services Networks. *Journal of International Commerce, Economics and Policy*, 6(3). <https://doi.org/10.1142/S1793993315500143>
41. Lee, J., Shin, HD. & Hong, S. (2021), Servitization of Global Manufacturing Business. *J Ind Compet Trade* 21, 565–584.
42. Lei, N. (2022). Research on Job Preference in China’s Internet Industry Through the Conjoint Analysis. *Journal of Industrial Integration and Management*, 7(03), 273-309.
43. Liao C, Xiang Z, Zhou W, Li Z, Li Y. (2022), Research on the Configuration of Value Chain Transition in Chinese Manufacturing Enterprises. *Systems*. 10(5):164.
44. Liu, B., Li, C. (2022), China in Global Value Chains. Opening Strategy and Deep Integration, World Scientific.
45. Liu, Y., & Kim, D. (2020). Understanding of Servicification Trends in China Through Analysis of Interindustry Network Structure. In *Springer Proceedings in Business and Economics* (pp. 55–64). Springer Science and Business Media B.V. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-30967-1_6
46. Liu, Y., Han, W., Zhang, Y., Li, L., Wang, J., & Zheng, L. (2016). An Internet-of-Things solution for food safety and quality control: A pilot project in China. *Journal of Industrial Information Integration*, 3, 1-7.
47. Lodefalk, M. (2013) Servicification of Manufacturing—Evidence from Sweden. *Int. J. Econ. Bus. Res.*, 6, 87–113.
48. Marshall, J.N., Damesick, P., Wood, P. (1987), Understanding the Location and Role of Producer Services in the United Kingdom. *Environ. Plan. A Econ. Space*, 19, 575–595.
49. Matthes, M., Kunkel, S. (2020), Structural change and digitalization in developing countries: Conceptually linking the two transformations, *Technology in Society*, 63.

50. Meckstroth, D.J. (2017) *The Manufacturing Value Chain is Much Bigger than You Think*; MAPI Foundation: Arlington, VA, USA.
51. Melitz, J.M. (2003), The impact of trade on intra-industry reallocations and aggregate industry productivity, *Econometrica*, 71 (6), pp. 1695-1725
52. Miller, R.E., & Blair, P.D. (2009), *Input-Output Analysis: Foundations and Extensions*. Cambridge, GBR: Cambridge University Press.
53. Ming-rong, W., Ming-xi, W. (2012), The Impact of Producer Services on Manufacturing Exports—Evidence from China’s Industrial Panel. *J. Tech. Econ. Manag.*, 4, 117–120.
54. Miroudot, S. (2016) *Services in global value chains: From inputs to value-creating activities*. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Trade Policy Paper, OECD, Paris.
55. Miroudot, S.; Cadestin, C. (2017) *Services in Global Value Chains: From Inputs to Value-Creating Activities*. OECD Trade Policy Pap., 197.
56. Müller, J., and Buliga, O. (2019), Archetypes for data-driven business models for manufacturing companies in Industry 4.0, International Conference on Information Systems 2019 Special Interest Group on Big Data Proceedings.
57. Natanelov, V., Cao, S., Foth, M., & Dulleck, U. (2022). Blockchain smart contracts for supply chain finance: Mapping the innovation potential in Australia-China beef supply chains. *Journal of Industrial Information Integration*, 30, 100389.
58. National Board of Trade (2012). *Everybody Is in Services —The Impact of Servicification in Manufacturing on Trade and Trade Policy*; National Board of Trade: Stockholm, Sweden.
59. OECD (2022) <https://stats.oecd.org/>.
60. Pattnayak, S. S., & Chadha, A. (2022). Servicification and manufacturing exports: Evidence from India. *Economic Modelling*, 108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econmod.2022.105756>
61. Pezzotta, G.; Arioli, V.; Adrodegari, F.; et al. (2022) Digital Servitization in the Manufacturing Sector: Survey Preliminary Results, Conference: APMS - Smart Manufacturing and Logistics Systems: Turning Ideas into ActionAt: Gyeongju, South Korea.
62. Pisano, G.; Shih, W. (2012) *Producing Prosperity: Why America Needs a Manufacturing Renaissance*; Harvard Business Review Press: Cambridge, MA, USA.

63. Pomfret, R. (2019). The Eurasian Landbridge and China's Belt and Road Initiative: Demand, supply of services and public policy. *World Economy*, 42(6), 1642–1653. <https://doi.org/10.1111/twec.12758>
64. Ramaswamy, V., Ozcan, K. (2016), Brand value co-creation in a digitalized world: An integrative framework and research implications, *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 33 (1), pp. 93-10.
65. Reddy, K., & Sasidharan, S. (2022). Servicification and global value chain survival: Firm-level evidence from India. *Australian Economic Papers*, 61(3), 455–473. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8454.12255>
66. Rodrik, D. (2016) Premature Deindustrialization. *J. Econ. Growth*, 21/1, 1–33.
67. Rueda-Cantuche, J.M.; Neuwahl, F.V.R.; Delgado, L. (2012) The Adjustment Capacity of the European Economy Examined with an Input–Output Based Key Sector Analysis: Towards a Review of the European Single Market; European Commission Joint Research Centre: Brussels, Belgium.
68. Shen L, Sun C, Ali M. (2021), Path of Smart Servitization and Transformation in the Textile Industry: A Case Study of Various Regions in China. *Sustainability*. 13(21).
69. Šidlauskaitė, B.; Miškinis, A. (2013) The Development of Economic Structure and Inter-Industry Linkages. *Ekonomika*, 92, 32–34.
70. Skare, M., de Obesso, M.M., Ribeiro-Navarrete, S. (2023), Digital transformation and European small and medium enterprises (SMEs): A comparative study using digital economy and society index data, *International Journal of Information Management*, 68.
71. Su, J., Ma, H. and Zhang, S. (2021), Developing innovation capabilities for upgrading in global value chains: evidence from China, *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, Vol. 16 No. 8, pp. 1654-1676.
72. Thangavelu, S.M., Wang, W., Oum, S. (2018). Servicification in global value chains: Comparative analysis of selected Asian countries with OECD, *The World Economy*, 41(11), 3045-3070.
73. The American Enterprise Institute and The Heritage Foundation (2022) China Investment Tracker, <https://www.aei.org/china-global-investment-tracker/>.
74. Timmer, M.P.; Erumban, A.A.; Los, B.; Stehrer, R.; De Vries, G. (2014) Slicing Up Global Value Chains. *J. Econ. Perspect*, 28, 99–118.
75. Timmer, M.P.; Los, B.; Stehrer, R.; De Vries, G. (2012) Fragmentation, Incomes and Jobs. An Analysis of European Competitiveness; ECB: Frankfurt, Germany.

76. Tsigas, M., Wang, Z. and Gehlhar, M. (2012), "How a Global Inter-Country Input-Output Table with Processing Trade Account Can be constructed from GTAP Database." Paper presented at the 15th annual conference for global trade analysis, July 28, Geneva.
77. UNCTAD (2021), Impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic on trade in the digital economy, Vol. 19, Technical Notes on ICT for Development No (2021).
78. UNCTAD (2023) <https://unctadstat.unctad.org/EN/>.
79. Verhoef, P.C., Broekhuizen, T., Bart, Y., Bhattacharya, A., Dong, J., Fabian, N., Haenlein, M., (2021), Digital transformation: A multidisciplinary reflection and research agenda, Journal of Business Research, 122.
80. Wolfmayr, Y. (2008) Producer Services and Competitiveness of Manufacturing Exports. Available online: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/23752002_Producer_Services_and_Competitiveness_of_Manufacturing_Exports.
81. Xing, Y. (2016). Global Value Chains and China's Exports to High-income Countries. International Economic Journal. 30.
82. Yu, L., Zhao, D., Niu, H., Lu, F. (2020), Does the belt and road initiative expand China's export potential to countries along the belt and road? China Economic Review, 60.
83. Yu, Z., Xiao, Y., Gu, X., Xie, X. (2022), Does imported producer service affect manufacturing export? Evidence from China, Singapore Economic Review, 67(3).
84. Zhang, C. (2019). Research on the fluctuation and factors of China TFP of IT industry. Journal of Industrial Integration and Management, 4(04), 1950013.
85. Zhang, J., Sun, X., Yuan, F., Liu, X. (2023), Which type of servitization promotes firm performance: Embedded or hybrid?, Economic Modelling, 126

Appendix

Table A. Servicification of European countries manufacturing with Chinese ICT services in 1995-2018 (% of gross exports)

	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Austria	0.5	0.5	0.7	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.8	0.9	0.8	1	1.2	1.3	1.3	1.6	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.5	1.9	2.1	2.4	2.6	3.3
Belgium	1	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.8	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	1.1	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.5	1.1	1	1.1	0.9	1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.6	2.1
Bulgaria	0.8	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.8	0.9	0.9	1	1.1	1.3	1.9	1.6	2.2	2.4	1.8	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.3	1.7	2	2.2	2.3	2.9
Croatia	0.4	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.7	0.7	0.9	0.9	1.1	1.3	1.7	1.9	1.9	2	1.5	1.6	1.5	1.4	1.3	1.5	1.7	1.7	1.9	2.3
Cyprus	1.1	1	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.8	1.9	2.1	2.2	1.9	1.9	1.8	1.9	2.2	1.6	1.7	1.7	1.3	1.5	1.9	2	2.3	2.4	3.2
Czechia	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.9	1.1	1.4	2.3	2.4	2.7	2.8	3.7	4.5	4.3	4.4	4	3.1	2.9	3.3	3.7	3.7	4.1	5.2

Denmark	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	1.1	1.3	1.5	1.4	1.5	1.7	1.6	1.5	1.8	1.6	1.7	2.2	2	2.2	2.8	3.3	3.4	3.9	4.9
Estonia	0.5	0.4	0.7	0.7	0.7	1.1	1.5	1.7	1.5	1.8	2.6	2.5	2.3	2.4	2	2.6	3.1	2.7	2.8	3.3	3.7	4.2	4.7	5.8
Finland	0.9	0.5	2.1	2.6	0.8	1	1	1.1	1.5	1.8	2.3	2.8	2.7	2.7	2.6	2.3	2.5	2.5	2.5	3.2	3.8	4.3	4.6	5.9
France	1	1	1.3	1.2	1.1	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.7	2.1	2.5	2.3	2.3	2.6	2.4	2.4	2.5	2	2.5	2.8	3.1	3.4	3.8	4.7
Germany	1.7	1.8	1.8	1.5	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.6	1.7	2	2.3	2.4	2.7	2.7	2.3	2.5	2.6	2.6	2.7	3.4	3.8	4.4	4.7	5.9
Greece	1	1.1	1.3	1.3	1.2	2.5	1.7	1.8	1.6	1.8	2.3	1.8	2.1	2.1	1.6	2.2	1.8	1.6	1.8	2.3	2.7	3	3.9	4.1
Hungary	0.5	0.7	0.7	0.9	1	1.5	1.9	2.6	3.5	2.9	3.8	3.6	3.8	4.3	3.5	3.9	2.9	2.3	2.3	2.6	2.8	3.1	3.4	4.1
Iceland	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.7	0.9	2.3	1.8	1.7	1.2	1.5	1.5	1.6	2.1	1.4	1.7	1.7	1.4	2	2.1	2.3	2.4	2.7	3.7
Ireland	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.7	1	1.3	1.5	2	1.6	1.8	0.9	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.1
Italy	0.8	0.9	1	0.9	1	1.3	1.3	1.6	1.5	1.8	2	2.1	2.2	2.6	1.9	2.2	2.2	1.8	2.1	2.5	2.9	3	3.2	4
Latvia	0.6	0.7	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.8	0.8	1	1	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.6	1.6	1.4	1.3	1.8	1.5	1.8	2.1	2.6	2.7	3	3.6
Lithuania	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.6	1.4	1.2	1.2	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.2	2.3	1.2	1.5	1.2	1.4	2.1	1.8	2.1	2.6
Luxembourg	1.2	1.1	1.4	1.3	0.6	1.4	0.8	1	1.2	1.2	1.1	1.3	1.1	1.4	1.7	1.1	1.2	1.1	1.2	1.4	1.6	1.8	2	2.6
Malta	0.8	0.8	1.1	0.8	1	1.3	1.5	1.9	1.2	1.4	1.3	1.4	1.2	1.6	1.6	1.5	1.2	1.3	1.5	1.9	2.1	2.3	2.3	2.9
Netherlands	0.8	0.6	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.9	1	1.1	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.6	1.5	1.4	1.6	1.7	1.5	1.7	1.9	2.2	2.9	3.2	3.9
Norway	0.6	0.9	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.1	1.1	1.5	1.2	1.5	1.8	1.7	1.7	1.9	1.4	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.8	2.3	2.7	3	3.3	3.9
Poland	0.8	0.9	1.1	1.1	1	1.1	1.3	1.5	1.6	1.9	2.1	2.3	2.4	3	2.5	2.6	2.1	1.9	2.1	2.6	3	3.3	3.6	4.1
Portugal	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.6	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	1	1.1	1.3	1.3	1.5	1.1	1.3	1.1	1	1.2	1.4	1.7	1.8	2.1	2.7
Romania	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.8	0.8	0.9	1	1.2	1.3	1.5	1.7	2	1.7	1.8	1.7	1.5	1.4	1.2	1.3	1.6	1.8	2	2.2	2.8
Slovakia	1.3	0.8	1	0.8	0.9	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.3	1.5	2	2.3	3.3	3.5	2.6	2.9	2.5	2.3	2.5	3.3	3.6	3.7	3.8	4
Slovenia	0.6	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.8	0.9	0.9	1	1.1	1.3	1.5	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.3	1.6	1.4	1.3	1.4	1.9	2.2	2.3	2.5	3.1
Spain	0.9	0.9	1	1	1	1.4	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.8	2.2	2.3	2.3	2.7	1.9	2.2	2	1.8	2.1	2.5	3.2	3.2	3.5	4.2
Sweden	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.9	1.5	0.9	0.9	1.1	1.5	1.5	1.4	1.3	1.3	1.4	1.7	2.4	2.8	3.3	3.9	3.9	4.3	5.2
Switzerland	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.8	0.8	1	1.1	1.2	1.2	1.5	1.5	1.7	1.7	1.5	1.6	1.5	1.3	1.4	1.7	2	2.4	2.6	3	3.6
United Kingdom	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.7	1.7	1.9	1.9	2.1	2.4	2.5	2.3	2.4	1.9	2	1.9	1.6	1.9	2.3	2.6	2.8	3	3.5

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, 2022